

Proposal ID 101056307	Call for Proposal CREA-CULT-2021-COOP	Topic CREA-CULT-2021-COOP-1	Type of Action CREA-AG-LS
---------------------------------	---	---------------------------------------	-------------------------------------

KPIs (Key Performance Indicators)

Please fill in the data for your project. At submission and grant preparation stage, the data will be on your planned indicators ; at reporting stage it should be the real indicators achieved (since the project start). The KPI tool should be updated with the latest available data for each periodic report (the KPIs are mandatory part of the project reporting). Please do not forget to tick the acknowledgement checkbox before submission.

CREA Culture

Location		
<table border="1"> <tr> <td>Country</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Country Spain</td> </tr> </table>	Country	Country Spain
Country		
Country Spain		
<table border="1"> <tr> <td>Country</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Country Italy</td> </tr> </table>	Country	Country Italy
Country		
Country Italy		
<table border="1"> <tr> <td>Country</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Country Portugal</td> </tr> </table>	Country	Country Portugal
Country		
Country Portugal		
<table border="1"> <tr> <td>Country</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Country Austria</td> </tr> </table>	Country	Country Austria
Country		
Country Austria		

Type of project, thematic area and types of activities		
Type of project:		
<input type="checkbox"/> Annual priority	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Audience engagement	<input type="checkbox"/> Digitalisation / New technology
<input type="checkbox"/> Internationalisation of careers and sectors	<input type="checkbox"/> Social inclusion	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Sustainability / Green deal
Sectors:		
<input type="checkbox"/> Books and publishing	<input type="checkbox"/> Architecture	<input type="checkbox"/> Art in public spaces
<input type="checkbox"/> Circus arts	<input type="checkbox"/> Craftwork	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Dance
<input type="checkbox"/> Decorative arts	<input type="checkbox"/> Digital arts	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Fashion and design
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Film/video arts	<input type="checkbox"/> Graphic arts/design	<input type="checkbox"/> Intangible cultural heritage
<input type="checkbox"/> Music	<input type="checkbox"/> Opera	<input type="checkbox"/> Other
<input type="checkbox"/> Painting, drawing	<input type="checkbox"/> Photography	<input type="checkbox"/> Puppetry
<input type="checkbox"/> Sculpture	<input type="checkbox"/> Sustainable cultural tourism	<input type="checkbox"/> Tangible cultural heritage - Historical sites and buildings

- Tangible cultural heritage - Libraries and archives Tangible cultural heritage - Museums Theatre

Type of socially marginalised groups that the project addresses:

- Addicts / substance abusers Children and Youth Current and former offenders and their families
- Homeless people Immigrants, Refugees, and Migrants People living in geographically remote / peripheral regions
- People living in poverty People living with health / mental health needs People of Differing Sexual Orientation / gender identity
- People of differing religious / political beliefs People with disabilities Racial/Cultural minorities
- Senior citizens Sexual orientation and Gender identity Unemployed people
- Victims of Human Trafficking Women and Girls

Objective (only for CREA CULT COOP (Mandatory)):

Innovation

Scale (only for CREA CULT LIT (Mandatory)):

Does the project contribute to any of the EU Commission political priorities?

- A Europe fit for the digital age - Empowering people through education and skills A Europe fit for the digital age - The digital age
- A European Green Deal - A just transition A European Green Deal - Climate change
- A European Green Deal - Preserving Europe's natural environment A European Green Deal - Sustainable Europe investment plan
- A new push for European democracy - A greater say for Europeans A new push for European democracy - Improving the lead candidate system
- A new push for European democracy - More transparency and scrutiny A new push for European democracy - Our democracy
- A new push for European democracy - Protecting our democracy A new push for European democracy - Special relationship with the European Parliament
- A stronger Europe in the world - A more active role A stronger Europe in the world - Defending Europe
- A stronger Europe in the world - Free and fair trade A stronger Europe in the world - The EU unique brand of responsible global leadership
- An economy that works for people - A union of equality An economy that works for people - Deepening our economic and monetary union
- An economy that works for people - Europe's social pillar An economy that works for people - Fair taxation
- An economy that works for people - Social fairness and prosperity An economy that works for people - Supporting small business
- Promoting our European way of life - Internal security Promoting our European way of life - Strong borders and a fresh start on migration
- Promoting our European way of life - Upholding the rule of law

Type of project participants

Types of participants:

Number of participants that are micro-enterprises:

2

Number of participants that are small enterprises:

0

Number of participants that are medium-sized enterprises:

2

Output, result and impact indicators (only at reporting)

Works, Events, Publications, Translations, etc

Number of events held:

7

Number of publications:

5

Number of literary translations (per language) (only for CREA CULT LIT):

Number of literary translations supported by the project

Employment

Number of days of work created for artists and professionals (only for final report):

20

Persons reached

Number of persons reached:

Country Spain		
Number of persons that participated in mobility activities (per country of origin):		
Male 117	Female 240	Non-binary 50
Total: 407		
Number of persons who accessed the work(s) (per country of origin):		
Number of persons who accessed the work(s) (per country of origin):		
Number of persons from that country who accessed the work(s) in person 407	Number of persons from that country who accessed the work(s) online 4500	Total persons who accessed the work(s) 4907
Country Portugal		
Number of persons that participated in mobility activities (per country of origin):		
Male 157	Female 161	Non-binary 50
Total: 368		
Number of persons who accessed the work(s) (per country of origin):		
Number of persons who accessed the work(s) (per country of origin):		
Number of persons from that country who accessed the work(s) in person 368	Number of persons from that country who accessed the work(s) online 6700	Total persons who accessed the work(s) 7068
Country Italy		

Number of persons that participated in mobility activities (per country of origin):

Male	Female	Non-binary
225	340	70
Total: 635		

Number of persons who accessed the work(s) (per country of origin):

Number of persons who accessed the work(s) (per country of origin):

Number of persons from that country who accessed the work(s) in person	Number of persons from that country who accessed the work(s) online	Total persons who accessed the work(s)
635	6700	7335

Total number of persons reached (all countries):
20720